

Convolutional Neural Network for Atherosclerotic Plaque Multiclass Semantic Image Segmentation in Transverse Ultrasound Images of Carotid Artery

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Abstract. Arterial stenosis is one of the most common diseases and if it is not discovered in time and adequately treated, it may have critical consequences, such as a debilitating stroke and even death. This is the reason why early detection is a number one priority. This disease occurs as a result of plaque deposition within the coronary vessel. The process of manually annotating plaque components is both resource and time consuming, therefore, an automatic and accurate segmentation tool is necessary. The goal of this research is to create a model that sufficiently identifies and segments atherosclerotic plaque components such as fibrous and calcified tissue and lipid core, by using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) on transverse ultrasound imaging data of carotid artery. U-net model was trained with dataset of 60 ultrasound samples, collected and annotated by medical experts during TAXINOMISIS project, and achieved 96.94% and 57.38% Jaccard similarity coefficient (JSC) for segmentation of background and fibrous classes, respectively. On the contrary, model had difficulties with segmentation of lipid and calcified plaque components due to dataset being imbalanced and small, which is shown with respective JSC values of 19.05% and 32.68%. Future research will focus on expanding current dataset with additional annotated ultrasound samples, with the goal of improving segmentation of lipid and calcified plaque components.

Keywords: carotid atherosclerotic plaque, convolutional neural network, ultrasound imaging data.

1 Introduction

Atherosclerotic vascular disease (AVS), or atherosclerosis, is a serious condition that affects millions of patients each year [1]. If not treated in a timely manner, it may have fatal consequences, such as an ischemic stroke. This is the reason why early detection

of AVS is very important. Due to the obesity, poor life choices and other factors, there is an increasing number of young individuals that are at the risk of atherosclerosis [2].

AVS is caused by significant blood flow reduction due to accumulation of atherosclerotic plaque within the coronary vessel. Over time, this plaque deposition, could lead to Transitional Ischemic Attack and stroke. Globally 1 in 4 adults over the age of 25 will have a stroke in their lifetime [3]. For a long time, it was thought that estimation of the Intima-Media Thickness (IMT) of the Common Carotid Artery (CCA) was best approach for the preclinical atherosclerosis diagnosis. In the recent studies it was shown that composition of carotid plaque has stronger association with vascular disease events [4], because stroke occurs when atherosclerotic plaques in the arteries suddenly rupture, leading to the obstruction of the blood flow to the heart or to the brain [5]. These vulnerable plaques that are prone to rupturing are usually characterized by thin fibrous cap and a large lipid area, with some calcified tissue present as well [6]. Correct identification of lipid, fibrous and calcified atherosclerotic plaque components is essential to pre-estimate the risk of cardiovascular disease, which would allow patients to be treated in a preventive and adequate manner.

Vast majority of techniques for identification of plaque components have been developed for multi-contrast magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data. In some research, instead of MRI, nuclear imaging and multi-detector computed tomography were used for detection. Even though aforementioned imaging data give quality and high-resolution view of atherosclerotic plaque, all of them have high cost and scanning limitations that hinder their usage in daily clinical practice. In contrast, B-mode ultrasound (US) is generally used for detection of plaque in vessels due to its availability, remarkably lower cost and ease of use. These advantages are the reason why the goal of this research is to develop dependable method for identification and segmentation of the atherosclerotic plaque components, by using Deep Learning methods on US imaging data of carotid artery.

Numerous research, that differ in both methodology and used imaging data, have been conducted on the topic of plaque segmentation. On MRI images, Clarke et al. [7] achieved satisfactory results using minimum distance classifier algorithm. On the other hand, Hofman et al. [8] tested multiple supervised learning algorithms on MRI images, but every model had problem correctly classifying calcification component. Rezaei et al. [9] proposed a set of algorithms for segmentation, feature extraction, and plaque type classification. A hybrid model using k-nearest neighbor (KNN) and the fuzzy c-means (FCM) algorithm was used to accurately segment the plaque area of intravascular ultrasound images. Perhaps, the best results were achieved by Athanasiou et al. [10] who used random forest algorithm for classification of features that were extracted from Optical coherence tomography (OCT) imaging data. They attained 0.71 and 0.81 Jaccard similarity coefficient for lipid and calcification components, respectively.

Despite aforementioned advantages, US imaging data are not extensively used in research on the topic of plaque segmentation, due to their low image quality with incorporation of significant noise [11]. This is the reason why most research that use US mainly focus on Intima-Media thickness (IMT) [12, 13] and not on vulnerable plaque assessment. Zhou et al. [14] were able to successfully localize plaque segments, but were not able to classify plaque composition. Lekadir et al. [15] presented

convolutional neural network (CNN) model for automatic classification of plaque composition that showed promising results. Problem with their approach is inability of CNN model to work with US image of the whole carotid wall, but with image of each plaque segment individually. This is inconvenient, because it requires manual extraction of plaque segments. Also due to the fact that their model only performs classification and not segmentation, there is a lack of clear visual representation of carotid wall plaque constitution. Nevertheless, this paper and numerous other research showed that convolutional neural networks are state-of-the-art in image segmentation.

In this paper, we describe use of a deep learning CNN (U-net) for segmentation of fibrous, lipid and calcification atherosclerotic plaque components on ultrasound images of carotid artery wall. The resulting segmented images show clear constitution of the atherosclerotic plaque, which makes process of patient risk assessment much more straightforward.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Dataset

First step in developing method for segmentation of the plaque components on US images is acquisition of a dataset containing original and annotated US images. Dataset used in this research was collected during TAXINOMISIS project, from Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade and Ethniko kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athinon, Greece [16]. Original dataset includes captured common carotid artery, carotid bifurcation and branches in transversal and longitudinal projections of 108 patients who went through US examination. Ultrasound examination was done in both B mode and Color doppler mode, so dataset consists of both types of images. To protect patient rights and safety, all imaging data were anonymized. From this dataset, only CCA images in transversal projections were used in the research, because they gave the clearest view of atherosclerotic plaque. Transverse projection allows visualization of the entire vessel wall as well as localization of plaques. This resulted in 67 images in total.

To ensure regularity and correctness in imaging data, data annotation was done by two independent clinical professionals. Process of data annotation has included labeling of different plaque components such as fibrous, calcified and lipid tissues. Labeling was done using “LabelMe” annotation program, which gave clear separation and distinction between different plaque components, as shown in Figure 3c. In the case of differences in the image interpretation, medical professional would come to a mutual agreement during an in-person meeting. It should be noted that fibrous component was prevailing component among all patients included in the dataset.

2.2 Image preprocessing

Image preprocessing is composed of steps shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Image preprocessing workflow

Since deposition of plaque takes place in carotid artery wall, it is necessary to make the wall focal point by removing tissue that is surrounding carotid artery in the imaging data. Extraction of carotid artery media was done by using two different CNN models that segment lumen and adventitia of the artery. Figure 2 depicts an ultrasound image with annotated adventitia and lumen.

Fig. 2. Example of annotated images. (a) original ultrasound image, (b) annotated carotid lumen area, (c) annotated carotid adventitia area

Outputs of two CNN models, after successful training on aforementioned data, are segmented lumen and adventitia of carotid artery. These outputs are then combined in a way that forms carotid artery media “ring” while removing unnecessary background tissue from the image. With this removal, images were left with large amount of background pixels which causes dataset to be highly imbalanced. This is the reason why unnecessary background was cropped out, leaving only Media in the images as shown in Figure 3b.

Fig. 3. Example of US image used in training process. (a) original ultrasound image, (b) extracted carotid artery media, (c) annotated plaque image

Process of plaque components segmentation is quite complex and time-consuming which is one of the reasons why U-net with data augmentation was used as a convolutional neural network model of choice. The dataset is split into two subsets: 90% of samples (60 images) were used as training dataset, while remaining 10% (7 images) represent the test dataset. Validation dataset was not used in this research, since its creation would result in additional reduction in number of samples in the, already small, training dataset. Optimal hyperparameters for the CNN model were found in the process of trial and error.

2.3 Methods

Multiclass semantic segmentation aims to assign semantic label to every pixel in an image. The topic of this research, atherosclerotic plaque components segmentation is defined as multiclass segmentation problem, where CNN is used to detect following four classes as shown in Figure 3c: background (part of the image outside the carotid artery media), calcified, lipid and fibrous plaque components. Input images have dimension of 256x256 pixels. Also, it was found that using images in RGB format, rather than grayscale, gave better results for segmentation problem. Pixel map for the model was labeled as follows:

- background (0) is annotated with dark blue color,
- fibrous plaque (1) is annotated with light blue color,
- lipid plaque (3) is annotated with yellow color,
- calcified plaque (4) is annotated with red color.

U-net architecture is used as plaque segmentation model as it was shown in numerous previous reports that U-net achieves great results for the segmentation problem on biomedical imaging data [17]. The U-net model consists of a contracting path to extract image features and an expanding path to upsample feature maps to their original size. U-net architecture that gave the best results using our dataset is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. U-net model used for segmentation of plaque components

To mitigate the effects of datasets small size, different image augmentations were applied to the input imaging data at the very beginning of the model. Combination of random horizontal flip and random rescaling by 10% was used in data augmentation layer. Left branch of the model is encoder with seven blocks, where each block contains two convolutional layers with kernel of size 3x3 pixels followed by 2x2 max pooling layer. Encoder blocks use convolutional layers with 24, 64, 128, 256, 512, 768 and 768 filters respectively. On the right side is a decoder branch that is symmetric to the contracting path. In each decoder block, 2x2 upconvolution and skip connection are followed by two more convolutional layers with 3x3 filters, and the last decoder block produces the segmentation mask with 1x1 convolution and sigmoid activation function. Activation function of choice is rectified linear unit (ReLU) for each convolutional layer. Segmentation map preserves the same height and width due to the fact that all convolutional layers are padded. This results in segmentation maps of the same dimensions as the input image. Even though data augmentation prevents overfitting to some degree, every other convolutional layer was followed by dropout layer as an extra measure for overfitting problem.

Training process lasted for 100 epochs. Numerous optimizers were tested, but it was shown that results did not differ by much, so Adam was used in the final model. On the other hand, results were drastically different depending on the choice of a loss function. Some of the loss functions that are often used in segmentation tasks, like categorical cross-entropy, had some issues with this dataset due to high class imbalance. In Figure 5, this imbalance is clearly showed by number of pixels that are part of the background or fibrous tissue class.

Fig. 5. Imbalance present in the dataset. y-axis shows the number of pixels present in one image sample and x-axis shows four classes present in imaging data

To try to lessen the effects of this imbalanced dataset, custom weighted loss function that combines dice loss and categorical focal loss was used. Weights were calculated according to number of pixels for each class, resulting in classes 2 and 3 (lipid and calcified plaque components) having larger weights values due to lower number of pixels belonging to these two classes. These calculated weights for each class are: [0.38 0.95 5.14 7.24].

3 Results and Discussion

In segmentation tasks Jaccard similarity coefficient (JSC) is often used, so it was decided to use it as evaluation metric in this research as well. JSC is computed as Intersection over Union between annotated image (ground truth) and segmentation mask predicted by U-net model. Mean JSC value, as well as JSC values for each class, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Class-wise and mean JSC scores

Classes	JSC score values [%]
Background class	96.94
Fibrous plaque class	57.38
Lipid plaque class	19.05
Calcified plaque class	32.68
Mean	51.52

Results in Table 1 evidently show that U-net model generally segments fibrous component correctly, but has difficulties correctly segmenting lipid and calcified plaque components. This problem occurs due to small dataset size, dataset imbalance and low

quality of ultrasound imaging data. Looking at predicted segmentation mask of one ultrasound image example presented in Figure 6c, couple of problems could be spotted. Generally, model correctly classifies type and location of every plaque component, but have trouble correctly segmenting shape and size of lipid and calcified plaque classes. Some of lipid plaque components are too large, due to the fact that surrounding fibrous tissue was wrongly classified as lipid plaque.

Fig. 6. Original ultrasound image (a), annotated mask (b), U-net model prediction (c)

These results are hard to compare to other methods since there isn't other research done on the topic of plaque components segmentation in ultrasound imaging data, but looking at segmented masks and JSC scores, it can be deduced that some classes, trained with current dataset, could not be segmented with the accuracy that could be used in clinical practice. However, current research set the basis for further investigation with the focus on improving segmentation of lipid and calcified components, as well as overall segmentation ability of the model. One of the steps that would undoubtedly enhance segmentation capabilities of the model would be training on larger dataset.

4 Conclusions

In this research deep learning method for segmentation of different plaque components of carotid artery in ultrasound imaging data was developed. Created model, based on modified U-net architecture, was trained on 60 ultrasound samples annotated by medical professionals. The training dataset showed to be heavily imbalanced which prompted the usage of a custom weighted loss function that combines dice loss and categorical focal loss. While achieving good results for segmentation of background and fibrous classes (96.94% and 57.38%, respectively), developed model had problem correctly segmenting lipid and calcified plaque components (19.05% and 32.68%, respectively), mainly due to the heavy class imbalance and small dataset size. There is a strong indication that larger dataset would provide better segmentation results.

Future research will focus on expanding current dataset with additional annotated ultrasound samples, with the goal of improving segmentation of lipid and calcified plaque components.

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